

THE NOTION ONOMASTIC SCOPE

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Annotation: *This article seeks to advance the field through a theoretical discussion of onomastic issues from a corpus linguistic point of view. It presents an overview of the linguistic status, meaning and grammar of proper names in order to highlight aspects, and peculiarities of onomastic scope of Uzbek language.*

Keywords: *common noun, proper noun, toponym, polysemantic, lexicology, grammar.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola onomastik masalalarni korpus lingvistik nuqtai nazardan nazariy muhokama qilish orqali sohani rivojlantirishga qaratilgan. Unda o'zbek tilining onomastik qo'llanish sohasi tomonlari va o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini yoritish maqsadida otlarning lisoniy holati, ma'nosi, grammatikasi hamda o'zbek tilining onomastik skop xususiyatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zi: *turdosh ot, atoqli ot, toponim, ko'p ma'noli so'z, leksikologiya, grammatika.*

Reality, material world which surrounds us is very complex, rich, multisided and different, and it differs from the essence, state, form, appearance and task of the things and phenomena which comprise them. The word used as a term common noun expresses partially these features which belong to the category of noun.

Naming things and phenomena, essence and actions in groups in general is peculiar not only to common nouns, but also to other types of words. For example, any colour in the nature and its any shade are reflected in the notions of “colour” and “shades”. All the notions on the things and phenomena which suit people's taste, good will, and aesthetic requirements are expressed by the help of the word “good”, and its opposite is expressed by the word “bad”. Generalizing nomination of the notions like these is peculiar to all parts of speech. The fact that in the history of humanity, in the history of a society a language does not only fulfil its function of thinking by generalizing, and some things and phenomena, and objects which are named are important for the people's life requirements who name them and the fact that those

objects have some differential features in comparison with others, played an important role. For instance, people gave separate names for each river, lake, and spring to differentiate them from each other in the regions where they live: Amudarya, Syrdarya, Zarafshan, Tashbulak, Kutirbulak and the like.

It means that proper names appeared as a result of naming things and phenomena as well as objects separately, and one by one. In case there was no such necessity they used to be satisfied with their general names.

The generalizing ability is the highest point of human being's thinking. If in case there was not such ability of a human being a language would consist of millions, billions of words and grammatical means and would be super difficult and vague and they would cease to be a phenomenon to be studied and perceived.

Science found out the existence of 100000 smell in the nature. Roses had more than 50 fragrances. But they are generalized by using several words and word combinations in Uzbek including *уйд, ус, буй* or *сассц, хушбуй, бадбуй, уидли, and ёцимли уид*.

So, naming of things and phenomena separately through proper names is the result of specific requirements, rules and laws.

Common nouns and other types of common nouns are well studied in comparison with proper nouns in linguistics. It can be noticed from the fact that common nouns and other types of parts of speech in Uzbek were widely analyzed and described on the basis of all their linguistic features.

There is the same thing about proper nouns. As only 4 or 5 types of proper nouns are mentioned in the existing lexicology, grammars, spelling rules and dictionaries and in analyzing various linguistic features materials of proper nouns are simply avoided.

Appropriate defining and grounding the essence and linguistic functions of proper nouns is mainly connected with collecting maximum material in concrete languages and proper noun materials in languages in general, and quantity volume of these names, their place in the word stock, defining the proportion, and the limits of proper noun types like in common nouns. In this case, particularly it is important to define clearly scientific criteria, requirements and provisions which meet the requirements of so called proper noun as a linguistic unit (onomastic category). As such scientific measure will enable to differentiate and limit a word which is called a proper noun from other common nouns and adjacent vocabulary phenomena.

Defining the existing proper noun types and the quantity in a concrete language will facilitate being aware of the circle of proper nouns and their spread in onomastic field in that very language.

This problem is interpreted in the research in connection with the notion of onomastic scope.

Initially the term "toponymic" scope" was used by V.N.Toporov⁴¹ and later A.V.Seperanskaya in her copied V.N.Toporov and used the terms "onomastic scope" and "toponomic scope"⁴².

"The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" explains the word кулам (scope) in the following way: "The spread of some activity, the scope, and volume; the degree of development and reaching the top"⁴³. In the given explanation the meanings "spread of some activity, the scope, and volume" can be applied to "onomastic scope". As onomastic scope defines the limits of existence of proper names in that language, its limits and indicates it quantity and volume.

The word "пространство" is polysemantic: it expresses 1) space, place, empty space in philosophy; 2) in simple meaning: wide space, field, place, gap; 3) vast space on the land surface⁴⁴.

This term can be used as onomastic level, onomastic field. But the onomastic notion, we are considering, expresses three features: 1) the existence of proper nouns in certain language; 2) their spread limit in the language; 3) the volume of onomastic vocabulary in the language. The terms level and field are narrow to express this meaning. Therefore we think it will be appropriate to replace the word пространство with the word кулам (scope). The meaning of this word is wide and is suitable for the meaning of the mentioned notion. It is also understood by the given explanation.

A.V.Superanskaya defines the appropriateness and convenience of the onomastic scope in the example of toponomic scope in the following way: ("Этот термин удобен тем, что он подразумевает пространственное размещение имени и именуемых объектов, т.е. нахождение их в некотором отдалении друг от друга, что соответствует размещению их на поверхности земного шара, а также за его пределы") ("Convenience of the term is that it enables to

know the places of the names and named objects in the space, and determines their distance from each other and placement on the surface and out of it"⁴⁵.

The term onomastic scope is also used in the meaning of general nomenclature (inventory), collection of proper nouns in a concrete

language. This inventory, according to A.V. Seperanskaya, as follows: “ — это сумма имен собственных, употребляющихся в языке данного народа для именованя реальных, гипотетических и фантастических объектов” (“Onomastic scope is a set of proper nouns in certain folk language and serves to name real, unreal and imaginary objects”)⁴⁶.

It is important to note that some scopes are not limited by the division mentioned and they, in their turn, are divided into further more smaller scopes.

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